

A Study on Consumer Preference and Awareness on Brand of Laptop with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

S. Malini

Assistant Professor, KG College of Arts and Science,
Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Computer is a remarkable machine. People are living in the processor age today and most of our daytime activities cannot be accomplished with any using computers. Communication system depends and the computer without computers internet is not possible. People use computers when and wherever they requires. Computers are worn in Schools, Hotels, Banks and grocery shops and in house also for various purposes. When people are gasp in the computer age and slowly computer has become such a dire need of life that it is difficult to picture life without it. Computer is affecting every sphere of our life. It affected government, business, entertainment, education, legal practice, defense and home. Computer has become a crucial and multipurpose tool. Supercomputers can predict weather; embedded computers make stylish devices like washing machines that bleep when washing is completed or the automobile that give you warning before contravention down.

KEY WORDS: *Communication system, Supercomputers, electronic machine, processor users*

INTRODUCTION

Computer is a remarkable machine. People are living in the processor age today and most of our daytime activities cannot be accomplished with any using computers. Communication system depends and the computer without computers internet is not possible. People use computers when and wherever they requires. Computers are worn in Schools, Hotels, Banks and grocery shops and in house also for various purposes. When people are gasp in the computer age and slowly computer has become such a dire need of life that it is difficult to picture life without it. Computer is affecting every sphere of our life. It

affected government, business, entertainment, education, legal practice, defense and home. Computer has become a crucial and multipurpose tool. Supercomputers can predict weather; embedded computers make stylish devices like washing machines that bleep when washing is completed or the automobile that give you warning before contravention down.

NEED FOR COMPUTER LITERACY:

Computers have surprised up the world. They have made us reliant upon them. People are expecting them to be present at every rest: the reservation counter, the microwave cooking or even pouring a car. Now that computers have enthused in our society so quickly, one needs, at least the essential computer skills to chase one's career goals and function efficiently and effectively, experts say that computer literacy is the require of today and voice of tomorrow to stay alive in the fast changing world of computers. For most of the populace computer literacy is limited to using the keyboard for type a document or making use of it for the calculation.

Computer: The Definition:

Precisely, "Computer is an electronic machine for performing mathematics and logical operations", or "Computer is a machine or flexible machine to process data and changes it into information".

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

A great diversity of laptops is now accessible in the market for the wants of the customers. There are a lot of brands with its unique specialty and with universal computing needs. Some may have extra external facilities, some may have extra facilities in dispensation and a number of may have extra

beautiful features like slim replica, wide screen and the like. The pace of the laptop also varies from brand to product. So there are some special skin tones which motivate the client to choose a particular brand of laptop. Hence a dealer needs to give sufficient support to his product from end to end advertising and other promotional labors on their special features.

In Tamilnadu, Coimbatore district is one of the significant education centre's with schools, colleges and universities at the same time it is a significant business centre too. Utility of processor in the field of teaching and business got its impetus in Coimbatore district. As long as the usefulness is high the varieties they use also augment. There may be a exact reason behind each product for the preference of processor users. Hence the investigator has made an effort to find out the reason why the customers go for an exacting brand and also to analyze that on which basis the populace prefer a particular brand.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The present revise is carried out in arrange to make an attempt to examine consumer preference and consciousness on brand of laptop with particular reference in Coimbatore city. This study mostly focuses its attention on the product preference. It does not wrap other connected areas.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The following are the objectives of the present study

1. To analyses the product preference of laptop user.
2. To trace the abstract ideas of the brand preference of laptop.
3. To study the factors influence of laptop users.
4. To offer the synopsis of findings, suggestion and conclusion.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The present study has been basically intended as a 'Expressive Study' with 'survey' as the method of research. A well structured survey was constructed and validate by the researcher for the compilation of primary data. A pilot learn has been made with 10 respondents before conduct the original training for check out the viability of the survey.

COLLECTION OF DATA:

This study is base on both primary and secondary information The required main data were composed from the students and professional by using the questionnaire construct and validated by the

investigator. The minor data were collected from the available and unpublished books, records, journals, newspapers, magazines, websites and the like. For this reason various universities and institution were visited by the canvasser.

SAMPLING DESIGN:

The researcher has follow the method of multi stage chance sampling for collect data from students and professional in Coimbatore city. The study was conduct among 120 respondents comprise 60 students, amongst them are 30 male and 30 female and 60 professionals.

GEOGRAPHICAL COVERAGE OF THE STUDY:

The learning has been confined to the metropolis of Coimbatore. This city is selected for the study as it has pertinent and positive variables of the learning. This city is describe as a city, which is recognized for its education centres and rising business. There are colleges and schools in and about the city. There are a lot of companies, in this metropolis who are having the maximum use of laptops. So the canvasser wants to select this region.

FRAMEWORK OF ANALYSIS:

The data were collected, oblique, tabulated and analyze using statistical technique. Data collected during survey were presented in a master table. From the master board sub-tables were ready. The statistical technique used in this revise are percentage analysis, Chi-square test analysis and Garrett's ranking technique analysis.

HYPOTHESES:

1. There exist no connection between the age of the respondents and the product preference.
2. There exists no connection between the occupation and the product preference
3. There exists no connection between the educational qualification and the product preference.
4. There exists no connection between the monthly income and the product preference.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

Although a number of brand are artificial in the laptop manufacturing the researcher has selected only seven to ten brands for the revise, as they are the the majority popular brand in the laptop marketplace. The brands the canvasser taken for study are HCL,

Lenovo, Compaq, Dell, LG, Toshiba, HP, Acer, IBM and Sony Vaio.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS:

1. Out of the total 120 respondents, 74 respondents are in the age group of below 30. Another 24 respondents are in the age group of 30-40. Another 12 respondents are in the age group of 40-50. Another 10 respondent are in the age group of above 50.
2. Out of the total 120 respondents, 60 respondents are male. Another 60 respondents are female.
3. Out of the total 120 respondents, 53 respondents are the post-graduates. Another 47 respondents are the professionals. 12 respondents are graduates and the remaining 8 respondents belong to other educational.
4. Out of the total 120 respondents, 60 respondents are students. 26 respondents are Business & professional people. 18 respondents are Government employees and the remaining 16 respondents are self-employees.
5. Out of the total 120 respondents, 48 respondents income level are up to Rs.10,000. 33 respondents are in the income level of Rs.10,000-Rs.15,000. 25 respondents income level are above Rs.20,000 and the remaining 14 respondents belong to the income level of Rs.15,000-Rs.20,000.
6. Out of the total 120 respondents, 47 respondents are their friends. Another 30 respondent's source of knowledge is media. Another 25 respondents are their family and relations are the source of knowledge and the remaining 18 respondents belong to other source of knowledge.
7. Out of the total 120 respondents 20 respondents preferred 'Compaq'. 18 respondents preferred 'Lenova'. 17 respondents preferred 'Dell'. 16 respondents preferred 'HP'. 13 respondents preferred 'Acer'. 11 respondent preferred for Toshiba. 10 respondents preferred 'HCL'. 7 respondents preferred 'IBM' and the remaining eight respondents preferred the other laptop brands, such as LG, G7 and Sony via.
8. Out of the total 120 respondents, 46 respondents are single user. 38 respondents are having 1-2 laptop users in their family. Another 23 respondents are having 2-3 laptop users in their family. Seven respondents are having 3-4 laptop users in the family and the remaining 6 respondents are having above 4 laptop users in the family.
9. Out of the total 120 respondents, 104 respondents are recommending their brand and the remaining 16 respondents do not prefer recommending their brand.
10. Out of 120 respondents, 61 respondents are having quality as the reasons for recommending their laptop. 30 respondents are having speed process as the reasons for recommending their laptop. 23 respondents are having extra facilities as the reasons for recommending their laptop and the remaining six respondents belong to other reasons for recommending the laptop (good configuration and low cost).
11. Out of the total 120 respondents, 100 respondents are not accepted the idea to change the laptop and the remaining 20 respondents are accepted the idea to change the laptop.
12. Out of the total 120 respondents, 35 respondents are having high price as the reasons for changing the brand and their strength comes to 29 per cent. Another 35 respondents are having slow processing as the reasons for changing the brand and their strength comes to 29 per cent. Another 35 respondents are having low facilities as the reasons for changing the brand and their strength comes to 29 per cent, and the remaining comes to 13 per cent of the total.
13. Out of the total 120 respondents, 102 respondents are daily users. Another 13 respondents are weekly once or twice users and the remaining five respondents are monthly once users.
14. Out of the total 120 respondents, 61 respondents are working more than 3 hours with the laptop. 30 respondents are working 2-3 hours with the laptop. 17 respondents are working 1-2 hours with the laptop and the remaining 12 respondents are working up to 1 hour with the laptop.
15. Out of the total 120 respondents, 61 respondents are having moderate opinion regarding the price of laptop; another 30 respondents are having medium rate opinion regarding the price of the laptop. 22 respondents are having high rate opinion regarding the price of the laptop and the remaining seven respondents are having low rate opinion regarding the price of the laptop.
16. Out of the total 120 respondents, 61 respondents are having Rs.20,000-Rs.30,000 as the preferable price of the laptop. 42 respondents are having Rs.30,000-Rs.40,000 as the preferable price of the laptop. Another 12 respondents are having Rs.40,000-Rs.50,000 as the preferable price of the laptop and the remaining five respondents are

having above Rs.50,000 as the preferable price of the laptop.

17. Out of the total 120 respondents, 79 respondents are having internet facility and the remaining 41 respondents are not having internet facility.
18. Out of the total 120 respondents, 45 respondents are having wireless chord mode of internet connect and their strength comes to 38 per cent, another 35 respondents are having any wired option (Broadband) mode of internet connect and their strength comes to 29 per cent. 25 respondents are having wireless access point mode of internet connect and their strength comes to 21 per cent and the remaining 15 respondents are having other mode of internet connect and their strength comes to 12 per cent of the total.
19. Out of the total 120 respondents, 67 respondents are having virus problem in laptop and the remaining 53 respondents are not having virus problem in laptop.
20. Out of the total 120 respondents, 78 respondents reason for virus problem are using devices such as Pen drive and CD's and their strength comes to 65 per cent. Another 25 respondent's reason are using net and downloading and their strength comes to 21 per cent and the remaining 17 respondents are having both reasons for virus problem.
21. Out of the total 120 respondents, 73 respondents are not having difficulties in using the brand, and the remaining 47 respondents are having difficulties in using the brand.
22. Out of the total 120 respondents, 77 respondents are having non availability of service centers as their specified problem and their strength comes to 64 per cent, another 15 respondents are having slow process as their specified problem and their strength comes to 12.5 per cent, for another 15 respondents keyboard is the specified problem and their strength comes to 12.5 per cent and the remaining 13 respondents are having emission of heat as their specify problem in laptop and their strength comes to 11 per cent of the total.
23. Out of the total 120 respondents, 65 respondents are having one year as their warranty period. 24 respondents are having two years as their warranty period another 21 respondents are having three years as their warranty period. Another 10 respondents are having above 4 years as their warranty period.
24. In order to test relationship between age and the brand preference, Chi-square test is applied to test the hypotheses and concluded that there is

significant relationship between the age of the respondents and the brand preference.

25. The researcher found out that there is no significant relationship between the educational qualification of the respondents and the brand preference.
26. The researcher found out that there is no significant relationship between the occupation of the respondents and the brand preference.
27. The researcher found out that there is no significant relationship between the income level of the respondents and the brand preference.
28. It is observed from those factors that influencing the purpose of using laptop variables such as 'Educational purpose', 'All the above', 'Business purpose', 'Official purpose' and 'entertainment purpose' have occupied the first, second and third ranks respectively and other variables have occupied the fourth rank and fifth rank.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. Service centres for all brands of laptops must be established everywhere to make the service easy.
2. Time duration to charge the battery must be increased, so that the usage of time will increase.
3. The price of the laptop must be reduced so that all level of people can purchase and use.
4. Scratch paper must be stucked in the monitor to avoid dust and scratch.
5. Guarantee period or warranty period must be increased.
6. Free services period must be increased, to avoid cheating and services from non-experts.
7. Weight of the laptop must be reduced so that it will easy to carry.
8. Antivirus must be provided with the laptop with a long service period.
9. The preferable and essential softwares for the laptops must be provided with the laptop to avoid confusions.
10. Sound system must be improved to avoid extra speaker system.
11. Extra mouse can be provide by the company
12. It is better to be provided easy accessible

CONCLUSION:

Many respondents are aware of more popular brands of laptops in India, especially in Coimbatore city of Tamilnadu. They feel that the brand name of laptop tells them something about the products its quality, its utility and its technology. The most preferable brands are moderate in price and good in quality. The brand

preference is influenced by age, educational, qualification, occupation, income, quality and price of the laptop. Thus the researcher has found out that the price of the laptop, quality and portability influence the brand preference of the users are on the rise.

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